

Effect of Natural Biopesticide Neem and Commercial Chemical Pesticide Fipronil on Growth and Reproduction of Earthworm *Eisenia foetida*

Snehalata Anakaram

Dept. of Zoology, Vasant Rao Naik Mahavidyalaya, Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar
Affiliated to Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract - Study of effect of natural biopesticide Neem and commercial chemical pesticide Fipronil on Growth and Reproduction of Earthworm *Eisenia foetida* was conducted. Three treatment feeds were applied for feeding the earthworms; T1 – neem leaves as organic raw material, T2 - Soil mixed with Fipronil + Neem Leaves Waste, T3 - Soil + Garden Waste. The effect of these three different feeds on Growth and Reproduction of Earthworm *Eisenia foetida* was studied. The number of juveniles and growth of earthworms was enhanced in earthworms fed with neem leaves followed by garden waste and decreased in earthworms fed with Soil mixed with Fipronil + Neem Leaves Waste. This study explains the importance of naturally available biopesticides and the need of eliminating the chemical insecticides and pesticides.

Keywords - neem, *Eisenia foetida*, fipronil, growth, cocoon

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of pesticides and chemicals in the agricultural fields is a concerning factor as it is pressurizing the global environment by disturbing the flora and faunal diversity. The interaction of earthworm in pesticide infested soil can be used as a bioindicator for pesticide pollution. Ongoing application of chemical pesticides is harming both living and non-living beings while posing a threat, and pests are developing resistance to these pesticides by changing their genetic structure to survive [1]. Soil contaminated by insecticides presents a significant environmental concern that negatively affects the soil biota.

Biopesticides are produced from natural living organisms from the source of animals, plants and microorganisms with the potential of neutralizing plant infested pests in an ecofriendly way replacing the chemical pesticides which are environmentally unsafe. Neem is a value added, widely used remedy for controlling pests in storage grains. An experiment aimed at managing the pod borer pest in rice crops by applying a combination of vermiwash and botanical neem seed extract demonstrated an effective and eco-friendly approach to pest control, serving as a substitute for chemical pesticides [2].

This study also aims with special emphasis on need for use of biopesticide and replacing chemical pesticides by identifying the change in the earthworm activity and effect on vermicompost production a value added end product. Chemical stress caused by pesticides on earthworms is studied with respect to physiology, biochemistry and genetic parts of earthworms [3, 4].

Effect of acetochlor, an herbicide at higher concentrations of (20–80 mg kg⁻¹), revealed sublethal toxicity to *E. fetida* in terms of growth, numbers of juveniles per cocoon and cellulase activity which indicate as sensitive parameters to evaluate the toxicity of acetochlor on earthworms [5].

Studies on effect of inorganic chemical fertilizers on *Eudrilus eugeniae* Kinberg earthworms revealed the harmful impact on mortality of adult and juvenile earthworms [6]. *Eisenia fetida* is the standard organism utilized in terrestrial ecotoxicology, as it can be readily cultivated on a range of organic materials with brief production periods [7, 8]

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The earthworm species *Eisenia foetida* were collected from Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar, Maharashtra, India. Around 500 authenticated earthworms were cultured in a pot with natural day light condition. The feeding substrate for earthworms was shredded partially decomposed neem leaves and garden waste. Depending on the size of the pot, nearly 20 healthy adult earthworms were selected by hand sorting, weighed for introducing in the pot experiments. Experimental pots were set-up, T1 included soil mixed with neem leaves powder in the proportion of 50:50. T2 included soil mixed with fipronil + neem leaves waste. Fipronil was diluted in water in the proportion of 30 ml/litre. This water was later added in the soil (T2). T3 as Control consisted of soil mixed with decomposed garden waste. The moisture of the pot substrates was maintained by 70-80% during the experiment, by sprinkling water intermittently. The pots and cocoon trays were kept at normal temperature with natural light.

After partial decomposition of neem waste in the soil and ensuring of proper mixing of soil with fipronil, hand sorted selected earthworms with clear clitella were released in the T1, T2 and T3 pots. The experiment was set up in two batches.

The pot substrates were thoroughly examined every once in a week by placing the pot substrate in a tray for observing the cocoons, earthworm size and weight. Meanwhile the earthworms were also weighed and measured compared with initial weight and size taken. The mortality of earthworms was also monitored if any, in all treatment pots. The study included earthworm growth, reproductive attainment through rate of cocoon production. The cocoons were segregated aided through fine brush, counted and transferred to

small trays containing the substrates same as that of T1, T2 & T3. The trays were covered with moist jute cloth to prevent escape of earthworms. The final vermicompost produced was harvested. Harvesting was done manually by hand sorting and passing through sieve mesh.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Paired sample t test [9] was performed to rule out the significant difference between three pot experiments (T1, T2, T3) compared in respect to weight of earthworm and cocoon production using Software of GraphPad Prism 9.

III. RESULT & DISCUSSION

In the initial weeks, there was immense change in the behaviour of earthworms from pot T2 (soil mixed with fipronil + neem leaves waste), the earthworms eluded to the bottom layer of pot, minor dormancy was noted from pot T2 which was followed by mortality and growth retardation. There was enhanced weight gain in earthworms from the pot T1 followed by T3 (Graph No.01) [P value <0.0001****]. The final weight was compared to the initial weight of earthworms recorded before their release in the pots. The length of earthworms was also measured which was seen 1.5 folds increase in T1, 1.4 fold increase in T3 and 1.8 fold increase in T2 substrate (Graph No.1.1) [P value <0.0001****]. A study was conducted to assess the impact of the insecticides chlorantraniliprole and fipronil on the growth, reproductive potential, and avoidance behavior of the earthworm *Eisenia fetida* [10]. The results showed a significant decline in the growth, body weight and reproductive capacity of *E. fetida* with the lowest survival rate and the number of cocoons. Our study equivalent the findings of [10]. In a research designed to assess the impact of Fipronil on the earthworm *Eudrilus eugeniae* as a biological indicator confirmed that fipronil is harmful to the earthworm *Eudrilus eugeniae* [11].

Sexual maturity in earthworms was observed at 30-35 days in T1, 30-40 days in T3 and delayed in T2 pot experiment. Key findings of Lekshemasamy, M.M (2012) can be attributed to our present study [12]. The enumeration of cocoon production was performed per earthworm. The cocoon production was boosted in the pattern of T1>T3>T2 (Graph No.02) [P value <0.0357*]. In conformity with Bohlen, 2002 the consumption and grade of feed substrate fosters the sexual maturity in earthworms [13].

As per the studies of Gupta and Saxena, 2003 insecticides affect the reproduction rate in earthworms; sperm head abnormality even in low concentrations [14]. Another study also revealed the effect of

pesticide on Earthworm growth, reproduction (cocoon production, number of hatchlings per cocoon and incubation period) [15].

In an experiments conducted, the findings revealed that three pesticides (carbendazim, dimethoate, and glyphosate) made adverse effects on the growth and reproduction of the earthworm species, *Eisenia fetida* [16]. A study showed the Earthworm growth and cocoon production was significantly reduced at copper oxychloride exposure concentrations of 8.92 mg kg⁻¹ [17].

Biopesticides affect enzymatic activity in soil, which is essential for the transformation of organic matter, breakdown of xenobiotics, and cycling of nutrients. Neem oil has been found to improve dehydrogenase and phosphatase activity at suggested doses, whereas high doses decrease phosphatase activity [18].

Nutritious soil functions as a vibrant living entity that provides various ecosystem advantages. It is closely linked to sustainable agriculture, which is described as the capacity of a crop production system to perpetually produce food without harming the environment [19].

III. CONCLUSIONS

This study explains the importance of naturally available biopesticides and the need of eliminating the chemical insecticides and pesticides. Neem leaves and garden refuse can be transformed into beneficial end product vermicompost. Our findings clearly indicate that Neem leaves can be converted into a nutrient-dense vermicompost suitable for use on vegetable, commercial, and economic crops. This is the most effective way to transform waste into wealth.

The variation in food habitat could also alter the diversity of the gut microbiome in the earthworms. Parameters like growth, reproduction, zero mortality, and cocoons per earthworm can be improved by substituting chemically based insecticides and pesticides with greens or organic fertilizers

In conclusion, it can be said that earthworms serve as effective bioengineers for recycling organic waste. They function as natural bioreactors and can biologically decompose organic matter in a symbiotic relationship. They enhance soil fertility and play a critical role in overall crop yield. Further studies are aimed on studying the effect of different concentrations of fipronil.

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Graph 1.0: Growth performance of *Eisenia foetida* in three treatments

Grah 1.1: Growth performance (Length) of *Eisenia foetida* in three treatments

Table 2.0: Reproduction rate (Cocoon/Earthworm) of *Eisenia foetida* in three treatments

